

Co-creating a Citizen Science Toolkit for Climate Assemblies in Living Labs

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Abstract

Citizen science, living labs and climate assemblies are spaces that open participation to the public. This manuscript describes a novel methodological approach which involves building scientific knowledge through citizen science projects, developing innovative tools in living labs, and generating recommendations for policymakers raised in climate assemblies. In this case, the Ebre Bioterritori Living Lab serves as the hub for co-creating a citizen science toolkit for climate assemblies. Citizen science projects are carefully selected from diverse databases and platforms and are relevant to climate change action. Furthermore, the citizen science toolkit is co-created in the living lab, with activities designed around each citizen science project. The toolkit is tested by a group of people in the living lab before being deployed in climate assemblies for different stakeholders, including policymakers, facilitators, technicians, and citizens. The primary goal of the toolkit is to enable participants to acquire knowledge from citizen science projects and to ensure the inclusivity and accessibility of the participatory process to all living labs and climate assemblies. In summary, this research aims to create an inclusive, accessible, and effective citizen science toolkit that ultimately empowers citizens to take collective action on climate adaptation through participatory processes.

Keywords

citizen science, climate assemblies, deliberative democracy, climate adaptation, climate policymaking, bottom-up governance

Introduction

Citizen climate assemblies bring together randomly selected citizens to learn, deliberate and make recommendations on collective issues of the climate crisis, following a participatory action research mechanism (KNOCA, n.d.). In recent years multiple citizen climate assemblies have taken place at local, regional, and national levels around the world. Given their participatory nature and evidence-based approach, climate assemblies can be a perfect place for introducing citizen science practices, which can contribute to bottom-up policymaking, embracing multiple perspectives (Schade et al., 2021).

Citizen science projects have contributed to the research in multiple domains: social sciences (Bonhoure et al., 2023), environmental advocacy (Johnson et al., 2014) and public understanding of science (Bonney et al., 2016). Citizen science is not only a powerful set of methodologies but also a way to understand and practice research allowing citizens and researchers to collaborate in scientific research. In recent years, citizen science projects have undergone a significant evolution to become more genuinely participatory (English et al., 2018). These projects invite citizens to collaborate more closely with researchers and involve them in most parts of the scientific research process. Citizen science toolkits have been implemented successfully in contexts such as education (Bonney et al., 2009) or libraries (Perelló et al., 2019) with a powerful community of citizens engaged to participate in activities for generating new knowledge. This collaborative approach allows citizens not just to collect evidence but also to co-create scientific knowledge and, eventually, generate policy recommendations based on the outcomes obtained and, subsequently, force changes in policies.

One area where citizen science has the potential to make a significant impact is living labs (Veeckman & Temmerman, 2021). Living labs are perfect spaces where multiple stakeholders collaborate to co-designing projects for sustainable impact (ENOLL, n.d.). Thus, living labs can become an ideal interphase to introduce citizen science projects on developing sustainable solutions to complex social and environmental challenges. Living labs thus allow designing, re-designing, adapting, testing, and eventually deploying technologies and services that better meet the needs of users, engaging citizens to effectively tackle socio-ecological challenges. Therefore, they may lead to the creation of more innovative, effective, and sustainable citizen science projects that benefit the community and the territories.

In this paper, we present work-in-progress research that combines citizen science, living

labs and climate assemblies. Overall, we introduce how citizen science projects can be included in citizen climate assemblies and how living labs serve as a space for co-designing, testing the toolkit and eventually deploying citizen science projects in the local context of the living labs.

The CLIMAS project for creating a toolbox for climate assemblies

CLIMAS is a comprehensive project that seeks to create a toolkit for climate assemblies, which is co-designed, tested, and deployed in living labs. The project works with three climate assemblies and four living labs. In the context of the project, we will work with three climate assemblies (i.e., Catalunya, Edermünde, Riga) and four living labs (i.e., Chios Living Lab, Vilnius Living Lab, JRC Living Lab and Ebre Bioterritori Living Lab). Here we present the co-creation of a citizen science toolkit for climate assemblies built in the Ebre Bioterritori Living Lab.

Our proposal is to bring citizen science into climate assemblies and use living labs as a space for co-designing, testing and deploying tools within the community. Putting together a whole participatory approach lifecycle which includes: building scientific knowledge by means of citizen science projects, developing innovative tools in living labs and generating recommendations for policy-makers in climate assemblies. This process helps us to create evidence-based tools with and for society, considering the interests of different stakeholders and ensuring that the horizontal participatory process is inclusive and accessible for all the living lab community and subsequently by the citizens in climate assemblies.

Selection of relevant citizen science projects

As a starting point, we look for citizen science projects that research topics related to climate change action. We select projects from citizen science platforms and databases (e.g., EU Citizen Science (EU-Citizen.Science, n.d.), SciStarter (SciStarter, n.d.), Zooniverse (Zooniverse, n.d.)) with active projects relevant for understanding climate change impacts and, therefore, providing valuable knowledge to citizens, facilitators, and government body of climate assemblies. The idea is to compile a collection of projects that represent the diversity of topics and geographies to ensure those projects are relevant for living labs and consequently for climate assemblies. Beyond scrutinising European-wide initiatives, we collect requirements from all the living labs to understand the currently active projects

that they are working on in the local context. Additionally, we will open a call for citizen science projects that could be interested in being included in the toolkit for climate assemblies.

Co-creating a citizen science toolkit in the living lab

The citizen science toolkit is co-created in the Ebre Bioterritori Living Lab where, firstly, we define the plan for implementing the participatory activities. It requires the following aspects:

- Identify stakeholders and plan their engagement towards the development of the citizen science toolkit.
- Deployment of participatory toolkits and ITC infrastructure for facilitating participation in the living lab (e.g. Decidim (Decidim, n.d.)). ENOLL toolkits will be at the core of tools to develop the citizen science toolkit for climate assemblies.
- Deliver two informative hybrid sessions to foster a deep understanding of the project as well as the results from the process. The first session will be aimed at explaining the features of the CLIMAS project, as well as the planning and engaging stakeholders. The final session will focus on the main results and the outputs obtained through the participatory process as well as the next steps.
- Deliver a series of 4 on-site workshops using living lab methodologies. It implies: i) testing and validating existing citizen science projects for climate assemblies and evaluating the user's perception, ii) discovering and identifying user needs, goals, and values, iii) ideating innovative insights and proposing solutions for the citizen science toolkit. Finally, based on the feedback, iv) test and validate the developed citizen science toolkit.

We plan to carry out different activities in the Ebre Bioterritori Living Lab:

Co-design the toolkit. Create guidelines for the introduction of citizen science projects in climate assemblies.

- Define the attributes that make citizen science projects suitable for a climate assembly and select the most relevant projects based on the criteria. Projects may be relevant for a variety of reasons that should be assessed, including the topic's relevance, the significance of research findings, the project's leadership team accessibility, the opportunity to actively participate in the project, the alignment

with community concerns, and so on.

- Design activities around each citizen science project that can be beneficial for acquiring knowledge for the members of climate assemblies. These activities could range from actively participating in the citizen science project to inviting the experts involved in the citizen science research to participate as speakers in the assembly. Some projects have been previously adapted to another context (e.g., schools, libraries, hospitals, etc.). During the sessions, the participants propose activities in the context of climate assemblies.
- Redesign active citizen science projects or reactive non-active citizen science projects to tackle community concerns of the living lab and the climate assemblies. The community around living labs has the mission to redesign or reactive citizen science projects if these projects can be beneficial for the community.
- Potentially, create guidelines for generating a new citizen science project if a community concern is not being addressed by existing citizen science projects. In this case, we will create a viability plan that includes a set of needs for building a new project, ranging from funds to domain expertise.

Testing the toolkit. Once the toolkit has been designed, a group of people will test it in the living lab and/or climate assemblies. In this phase, we test the guidelines for the groups that are part of the climate assembly and the phases of the participatory process in which the activities fit better.

Deploying the toolkit. The toolkit is conceived to be used in climate assemblies, however potentially the living lab community can adopt some of the projects for being deployed and integrated into the regular activities of the living lab without further modifications.

Citizen science toolkit in climate assemblies

Finally, and once the Toolkit has been tested and validated in living labs and/or climate assemblies will ready to be deployed in climate assemblies. Climate assemblies have a very particular structure with different phases (e.g., learning, consultation, deliberation, decision-making, etc.) and bodies (e.g., governance body, group of experts, citizens, etc.). Citizen science relies on the basis that citizens can contribute to research as experts and acquire knowledge through this process. Some of the citizen science toolkit goals are to allow citizens to participate as experts in climate assemblies, to provide evidence to the governance body for designing the framing or choosing the topic discussed during the climate assembly; or to provide evidence to policymakers. Overall, we aim to deploy the

citizen science toolkit in different phases of climate assemblies and for different bodies.

Figure 1. Road plan for co-creating, testing and validating the citizen science toolkit for climate assemblies.

Conclusions

Citizen science has emerged as a powerful tool for engaging communities in various research domains, including climate action. Through citizen science, communities are more deeply involved in tackling societal concerns, leading to a greater sense of ownership and investment in the process. By leveraging the knowledge produced by citizens, citizen science can enhance the effectiveness of climate assemblies, making them more inclusive and accessible.

We are currently conducting ongoing research to co-create a citizen science toolkit specifically designed for climate assemblies. This toolkit is being co-developed and tested in living labs, where different participatory approaches are being used to democratize science, produce innovative tools and generate policy recommendations. Through this toolkit, we aim to raise awareness about the environmental and social issues that arise from climate change, ultimately facilitating social change.

Living labs are a critical component of this effort, as they provide a platform for experimentation and innovation. By bringing together stakeholders from diverse backgrounds, living labs enable us to develop and test solutions that are both technically and socially feasible. This collaborative approach is essential for achieving our goal of democratizing science and creating effective tools for addressing the challenges of climate change.

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